

Ion Exchange Column Studies with Aniline^ψ

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Ion exchange studies are mainly of two types : static and dynamic¹. The former involving the equilibrium of the system is of fundamental importance as it helps to identify the physicochemical interactions, and the latter, in general, is a complement to the static studies. Dynamic studies help to establish the column parameters, rate of exchange, rate of elution, eluent composition etc. which are different for different systems. Present study has been carried out to establish the dynamic condition suitable for the concentration and recovery of aniline in aqueous solution.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives aniline absorption efficiency of the column of resin WX8 in H⁺-form for different solvent media. It is evident that 100% efficiency is attained only in water when the flow rate is maintained at 10 cm³ min⁻¹. In very dilute acid medium (10⁻² N HCl), upto 55% of column capacity is utilised for the absorption of aniline. However, the results indicate that it is difficult to absorb aniline from highly acidic medium on the resin column.

TABLE 1—ANILINE ABSORPTION EFFICIENCY A_e (100 TW_x/COLUMN CAPACITY) OF THE COLUMN OF RESIN WX8 IN H⁺-FORM IN VARIOUS SOLVENT MEDIA AT DIFFERENT FLOW RATES

Solvent	Flow rate (cm ³ min ⁻¹)		
	10	20	30
Water	100	84	73.6
0.01 N HCl	55.2	49.1	42.4
0.1 N HCl	29.4	19.6	17.8
1.0 N HCl	7.4	6.7	6.7

Table 2 gives some important results chosen from the 36 runs carried out. It shows that water has very low elution efficiency E_e (13.5) and high elution volume V_t (10 dm³). 1N HCl, 1N aqueous ammonia and 0.1 N ammonia in 10% aqueous ethanol have about 100% elution efficiency at all the three flow rates, i.e. 10, 20 and 30 cm³ min⁻¹. It was also observed that 0.1 N and 0.01 N HCl, 0.1 N aqueous ammonia and 0.1 N ammonia in 20, 50 and 70% aqueous ethanol have the same elution efficiency (100%) at all the three flow rates. However, the total elution volume V_t and consequently the time required for complete elution of aniline suggests that 0.1 N ammonia in aqueous ethanol solutions are better eluents. Among the ammonical aqueous ethanols, 0.1 N ammonia in 10% aqueous ethanol (as it contains the minimum amount of the alcohol) is the best eluent at the rate of 30 cm³ min⁻¹ to desorb aniline from a column of resin Dowex 50W X8 in H⁺-form.

Experimental

Dowex 50W X8 (Dow chemical), styrene DVB copolymer based sulphonic acid cation exchange resin of relative degree of cross-linking 8 was taken in H⁺-form after proper conditioning regeneration and air-drying : mesh size, -20, +50; moisture content, 20.6%; capacity of the resin, 3.77 meq g⁻¹. Aniline (AnalaR) was used as such. Solutions of aniline were prepared in respective solvents. Double-distilled water was used wherever needed. The concentration of each solution was checked at $\lambda = 280$ nm.

Procedure : Weighed amount of air-dried resin was

TABLE 2—SOME IMPORTANT PARAMETERS FROM 36 RUNS CARRIED OUT WITH ANILINE ON DOWEX 50W X8 RESIN COLUMN IN H⁺-FORM IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS* AT VARIOUS FLOW RATES

Parameter**	10 cm ³ min ⁻¹				20 cm ³ min ⁻¹				30 cm ³ min ⁻¹			
	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)
TW _x	17.67	16.3	16.4	16.4	13.7	16.3	16.4	16.4	12.80	16.3	16.3	16.3
TW _t	2.20	16.20	16.38	20.71	2.6	16.4	16.4	16.2	2.0	16.13	16.4	16.2
E_e	12.45	99.38	99.87	126.2	18.9	100.61	100.0	98.78	15.60	98.95	100.6	99.38
V_t	10.0	1.5	1.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	8.5	1.3	1.5	5.0	2.0	1.3

* Solvents : (A) = distilled water, (B) = 1.0 N HCl, (C) = 1.0 N aqueous ammonia, (D) = 0.1 N ammonia in 10% aqueous ethanol.

** TW_x = Total amount of aniline in meq. exchanged by the column; TW_t = total amount of aniline in meq. eluted from the column; E_e = elution efficiency (100 TW_D/TW_x), V_t = total volume of eluent necessary for complete elution, dm⁻³.

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NOTE

slurried with distilled water and transferred to corning glass columns fitted with sintered glass discs of zero porosity. The resin in the column was back-washed and allowed to settle under gravity. The column parameters were as follows : bed length, 11.2 cm; bed volume, 8.9 cm³; void volume, 2.6 cm³; column capacity, 16.3 meq.

The study consisted of 36 runs. Each run consisted of two parts : exchange of aniline (concentration always 2 meq dm⁻³) from various solvent media at different flow rates was done in Part-A and elution of exchanged aniline from the column by various eluents at different flow rates was done in Part-B.

On completion of Part-A of each run, the resin column was washed with two bed-volumes of distilled water and then Part-B was carried out. Distilled water was used as both solvent and eluent in Part-A and -B of runs 1, 2 and 3. The flow rates were 10, 20 and 30 cm³ min⁻¹. In runs 4-12,

distilled water was used as solvent in Part-A and aqueous HCl of various concentrations (1.0, 0.1 and 0.01 *N*) were used as eluent in Part-B keeping the flow rates as before. Part-A of runs 13-36 were repetition of 1A. However, aqueous ammonia of strengths 1.0, 0.1 and 0.01 *N* were used as eluent in Part-B of runs 13-24 and 0.1 *N* ammonia in 10, 20, 50 and 70% aqueous ethyl ethanol solutions were used as eluents in Part-B of runs 25-36. Elution with each eluent was carried out at three speeds : 10, 20 and 30 cm³ min⁻¹.

References

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